

Supplementary material

"Contribution of V1 receptive field properties to corruption robustness in CNNs", ECAI 2024

1 VOneNets

VOneNet Model Family VOneNets [2] are hybrid CNNs, with a biologically-constrained fixed-weight front-end layer that simulates V1, called the VOneBlock, followed by a neural network back-end adapted from current CNN vision models. The VOneBlock is a linear-nonlinear-Poisson (LNP) model of V1 [7], consisting of a fixed-weight Gabor Filter Bank (GFB) [5], simple and complex cell [1] nonlinearities, and neuronal stochasticity [9]. The code for the VOneNet model family is publicly available at <https://github.com/dicarlo/lab/vonenet> under GNU General Public License v3.0.

GFB parameters The Gabor Filter Bank (GFB) contains Gabor filters with multiple orientations, spatial frequencies, and sizes. The parameters are randomly sampled from distributions of preferred orientation ($[0 - 180]$ deg), peak spatial frequency ($[0.5 - 11.3]$ cpd), and size/shape of receptive fields (both n_x and n_y in $[0.1 - 1]$). The BIOL variant samples the GFB parameters from empirical distributions [3, 4, 6, 8]. While orientation is sampled independently, the RF sizes along the perpendicular and parallel axes are sampled from a joint distribution, and a correlation is introduced between the RF size and the SF to match what is observed empirically (paper Figure 2).

2 Detailed Accuracies

All reported accuracies represent the top-1 accuracy on the validation datasets of Tiny ImageNet (for clean) and Tiny ImageNet-C (for corruptions). In the main text and paper Table 1 the accuracies are reported relative to the standard model ResNet18 and in the Supplementary material (Table 1 and Figure 1) they are absolute values.

Figure 1. BIOL and UNIF3 show consistent improvements in robustness. Absolute accuracies for ResNet18 (RN18), BIOL, UNIF1, UNIF2 and UNIF3 for the 15 corruption types at all perturbation severity levels. Accuracy represents top-1 (%). Perturbation 0 corresponds to no corruption (clean images).

Table 1. Absolute accuracies of ResNet18, BIOL, UNIF1, UNIF2 and UNIF3. Clean images and 15 types of common image corruptions (averaged over five perturbation severities). The value in parenthesis represents the standard error of the mean (n = 4 seeds). UNIF3 has the highest accuracy in all image types except clean, contrast, and pixelate (in favor of ResNet18, with BIOL coming very close behind), and except fog, brightness and JPEG (in favor of BIOL).

Model	Noise				Blur			
	Clean [%]	Gaussian [%]	Shot [%]	Impulse [%]	Defocus [%]	Glass [%]	Motion [%]	Zoom [%]
ResNet18	57.7 (0.27)	19.4 (0.19)	22.6 (0.26)	21.4 (0.16)	14.2 (0.32)	19.0 (0.21)	19.5 (0.49)	16.2 (0.57)
VOneResNet18 BIOL	56.14 (0.39)	22.49 (0.43)	27.05 (0.44)	22.42 (0.24)	14.5 (0.2)	18.82 (0.05)	20.01 (0.2)	16.26 (0.2)
VOneResNet18 UNIF1	56.05 (0.16)	20.69 (0.11)	24.93 (0.14)	21.78 (0.15)	14.15 (0.2)	18.62 (0.13)	19.35 (0.14)	15.94 (0.23)
VOneResNet18 UNIF2	56.07 (0.37)	20.71 (0.34)	24.81 (0.46)	22.17 (0.51)	14.23 (0.28)	19.04 (0.22)	19.3 (0.46)	16.04 (0.35)
VOneResNet18 UNIF3	55.62 (0.5)	22.7 (0.41)	27.16 (0.44)	22.53 (0.46)	14.95 (0.35)	19.15 (0.32)	20.39 (0.38)	16.7 (0.41)

Model	Weather				Digital			
	Snow [%]	Frost [%]	Fog [%]	Bright. [%]	Contrast [%]	Elastic [%]	Pixelate [%]	JPEG [%]
ResNet18	23.2 (0.57)	24.7 (0.27)	21.2 (0.29)	27.1 (0.25)	9.7 (0.14)	24.5 (0.45)	37.8 (0.35)	31.7 (0.41)
VOneResNet18 BIOL	26.75 (0.44)	27. (0.47)	22.55 (0.26)	28.94 (0.31)	9.38 (0.24)	26.67 (0.35)	36.63 (0.23)	36.65 (0.35)
VOneResNet18 UNIF1	24.56 (0.33)	24.8 (0.33)	21.32 (0.13)	26.62 (0.13)	8.73 (0.04)	25.23 (0.18)	35.88 (0.28)	33.66 (0.22)
VOneResNet18 UNIF2	24.44 (0.38)	25.14 (0.39)	21.88 (0.36)	26.77 (0.34)	9.15 (0.28)	25.33 (0.46)	36.09 (0.44)	33.21 (0.52)
VOneResNet18 UNIF3	26.77 (0.62)	27.05 (0.6)	22.31 (0.36)	28.43 (0.58)	9.12 (0.32)	27.3 (0.22)	35.68 (0.54)	36.42 (0.27)

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